

Supplementary Material: Nomogram for predicting survival of non-metastatic colon cancer patients

Jun-Peng Pei, Chun-Dong Zhang, Yu Liang, Cheng Zhang, Kun-Zhe Wu, Zhe-Ming Zhao, Dong-Qiu Dai

Table s1. Univariate analysis of the validation cohort.

Variables	3-y OS (%)	5-y OS (%)	Hazard ratio (95% CI)	P value
Age, years	85.3	78.5	1.022 (1.019–1.025)	<0.001
Gender				
Male	84.7	76.7	1 (Ref)	–
Female	86.8	80.5	0.781 (0.746–0.819)	<0.001
Histological grade				
Grade I	91.0	85.6	1 (Ref)	–
Grade II	87.5	80.2	1.330 (1.212–1.460)	<0.001
Grade III	76.4	68.7	2.053 (1.855–2.272)	<0.001
Grade IV	71.2	64.2	2.528 (2.121–3.012)	<0.001
AJCC 8th T stage				
T1	94.6	91.2	1 (Ref)	–
T2	93.5	89.3	1.240 (1.093–1.407)	<0.001
T3	85.7	77.7	2.319 (2.084–2.581)	<0.001
T4a	71.5	61.2	4.354 (3.849–4.926)	<0.001
T4b	62.3	51.5	5.655 (4.982–6.420)	<0.001
AJCC 8th N stage				
N0	90.9	86.3	1 (Ref)	–
N1a	86.7	79.5	1.401 (1.250–1.570)	<0.001
N1b	79.9	70.3	2.057 (1.858–2.278)	<0.001
N2a	77.1	63.3	2.639 (2.363–2.947)	<0.001
N2b	59.7	48.9	4.080 (3.674–4.530)	<0.001
Positive lymph nodes	85.3	78.5	1.096 (1.092–1.099)	<0.001
Tumor size, cm	85.3	78.5	1.007 (1.006–1.008)	<0.001
Retrieved lymph nodes	85.3	78.5	0.988 (0.986–0.991)	<0.001

AJCC, American Joint Committee on Cancer; CI, confidence interval; OS, overall survival; y, year.

Table s2. Multivariable analyses of the validation cohort.

Variables	Multivariable analysis 1		Multivariable analysis 2	
	Hazard ratio (95% CI)	P value	Hazard ratio (95% CI)	P value
Age, years	1.029 (1.025–1.033)	<0.001	1.027 (1.023–1.031)	<0.001
Gender				
Male	1 (Ref)	–	1 (Ref)	–
Female	0.851 (0.793–0.914)	<0.001	0.852 (0.794–0.915)	<0.001
Histological grade				
Grade I	1 (Ref)	–	1 (Ref)	–
Grade II	1.094 (0.949–1.262)	0.215	1.126 (0.977–1.298)	0.102
Grade III	1.278 (1.091–1.497)	0.002	1.326 (1.132–1.553)	<0.001
Grade IV	1.549 (1.189–2.017)	0.001	1.592 (1.223–2.074)	0.001
AJCC 8th T stage				
T1	1 (Ref)	–	1 (Ref)	–
T2	1.286 (1.055–1.566)	0.013	1.339 (1.099–1.630)	0.004
T3	1.923 (1.613–2.293)	<0.001	2.208 (1.856–2.627)	<0.001
T4a	2.929 (2.390–3.589)	<0.001	3.519 (2.880–4.300)	<0.001
T4b	4.174 (3.378–5.157)	<0.001	4.813 (3.901–5.938)	<0.001
AJCC 8th N stage				
N0	1 (Ref)	–		
N1a	1.304 (1.162–1.464)	<0.001		
N1b	1.873 (1.688–2.079)	<0.001		
N2a	2.329 (2.077–2.611)	<0.001		
N2b	3.691 (3.299–4.129)	<0.001		
Positive lymph nodes			1.100 (1.093–1.108)	<0.001
Tumor size, cm	1.001 (1.000–1.002)	0.005	1.001 (1.000–1.002)	0.017
Retrieved lymph nodes	0.977 (0.973–0.981)	<0.001	0.971 (0.967–0.976)	<0.001

AJCC, American Joint Committee on Cancer; CI, confidence interval; OS, overall survival.

Multivariable analysis 1, variables included, age, gender, histological grade, AJCC 8th T stage, tumor size, retrieved lymph nodes, and AJCC 8th N stage;

Multivariable analysis 2, variables included, age, gender, histological grade, AJCC 8th T stage, tumor size, retrieved lymph nodes, and positive lymph nodes.